
Evaluating EEG Acquisition Systems for Neuromodulation: Anti-Aliasing Filter Testing Methodology

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Neurostimulation, encompassing both invasive and non-invasive techniques, is crucial for treating conditions like epilepsy, Parkinson's, and psychiatric disorders. Scalp EEG is commonly used to study neurostimulation effects and optimize therapies. However, artifacts from neuromodulation devices pose a significant challenge. This study aims to present a simple method to test the anti-aliasing filter response of EEG amplifiers to ensure their effectiveness during neurostimulation.

Methods: Two high-density EEG systems were evaluated: System 1 (TI ADS1278 converter) and System 2 (TI ADS1298 converter). Each system was tested using synthetic signals to simulate neurostimulation artifacts, analyzed through continuous wavelet transform (CWT) and Welch power spectral density (PSD) estimates. The performance of each system was assessed based on its ability to handle out-of-band frequencies and minimize aliasing artifacts.

Results: System 1 exhibited superior performance with minimal aliasing artifacts compared to System 2. System 2's sinc3 filter resulted in significant sidelobes and contamination across the spectrum. Theoretical bode magnitude plots confirmed that System 1's anti-aliasing filter provided greater attenuation of out-of-band frequencies, enhancing its suitability for neurostimulation applications, despite a higher group delay.

Discussion: Selecting an appropriate EEG acquisition system is crucial for study design, with the ADC being a key component in preventing aliasing. Empirical results and theoretical analyses showed that System 1 outperformed System 2 in handling out-of-band frequencies, making it more suitable for neurostimulation studies. However, complete artifact removal requires additional tools beyond the anti-aliasing filter.

Conclusion: This study proposes a cost-effective method to test EEG systems for neurostimulation suitability, identifying System 1 as more effective in managing neurostimulation artifacts. Future work will extend this methodology to other EEG and MEG systems.

Keywords: Neuromodulation, Transfer function, Anti-aliasing, Deep Brain Stimulation, EEG, neuromodulation artifacts, continuous wavelet transform, power spectral density

1 INTRODUCTION

Neurostimulation is a rapidly growing field within neuroscience, neurology, and neurosurgery. It includes invasive and non-invasive approaches designed to apply electromagnetic energy to a target area. Invasive therapies have been recognized as an efficient treatment for diseases such as epilepsy (Fisher and Velasco, 2014), Parkinson's (Volkman, 2004), and psychiatric and headache disorders (Schwedt and Vargas, 2015). Other applications include cortical mapping as a prelude to neurosurgery and as a research tool used to study brain function. Over the last 3 decades several stimulation strategies, such as responsive neurostimulation (RNS), deep brain stimulation (DBS), vagus nerve stimulation (VNS), single pulse electrical stimulation (SPES), etc., have been used both in research and clinical practice. Scalp EEG has been established as a research tool to understand the effects of neurostimulation, as well as, to optimize stimulation parameters to increase the efficacy of neuromodulation therapies.

One of the major concerns with the usage of scalp EEG is the presence of artifacts generated by the neuromodulator. Multiple studies have reported this issue and several studies have described how to minimize their interference (Jech et al., 2006; Allen et al., 2010; Arafat et al., 2022; Giraldez et al., 2017). The waveform of the stimulation artifacts, generated by the implanted device, is in the form spike train containing a biphasic square wave with a pulse width of about 1 ms. The periodic nature of spike train leads to results in the bandwidth of the signal being large, in contrast with spontaneous EEG signal, which is characterized by a rapid decrease in spectral power of the signal with an increase in frequency (1/f spectral behavior) (Cohen, 2014). The necessity of a well-designed anti-aliasing filter in the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) chipset of the EEG amplifier is even more critical when acquiring EEG data with neurostimulation artifacts. The importance of a properly designed becomes further paramount when acquiring EEG with Neurostimulation Artifact. Therefore, EEG amplifiers must be evaluated from the point of view of the intended application and not only the nominal specifications. This evaluation is even more significant considering the high cost of such systems, often surpassing thousands of dollars. (Ledwidge et al., 2018).

In this study, we present a relatively simple method of testing framework to estimate the transfer function of the anti-aliasing (AA) filter response of the EEG amplifier, which could ensure its fitness with regard to data acquisition while neurostimulation is active. The devices required for this testing framework are relatively inexpensive and easily obtainable, making it viable in any lab. Furthermore, the knowledge of the anti-aliasing filter response can provide a better understanding of what sampling frequency to select for a specific analysis. In this study, we evaluated two similar nominal performance research-grade high-density EEG acquisition systems. We assessed their performance using spectral decomposition techniques for recording an artificial electrical signal. The choice of the recommended acquisition system was based on its performance with an in and out-of-band synthetic signal.

2 METHODS

2.1 EEG system specification

In this study, we estimated the filter-response of 2 systems containing two different ADC chipsets:

- System 1: contains Texas Instruments (TI) ADC chip ADS1278.
- System 2: contains Texas Instruments (TI) ADC chip ADS1298.

2.2 Prerequisite Testing Equipments

Each system was connected to a laptop with EEG acquisition software and the cap was placed in a recipient with saline solution (0.875 M), as instructed by vendor. We used a USB-connected sound card, Sound Blaster G1, with a 3.5 mm output port to generate the desired synthetic signal. The sound card was controlled using an in-house MATLAB algorithm and connected to the saline solution bucket via a 3.5 mm to 2-Male RCA adapter cable. The experimental setup diagram can be seen in Figure 1. We performed 2 tests for each acquisition system. The sampling rates of both systems were set to 1000 samples per second (SPS) with Nyquist frequency of 500 Hz.

2.3 Synthetic signal generation

We tested the AA filter response using two type of synthetic signals:

- Swept sine: synthetic logarithmic chirp at 200 kSPS with frequencies ranging from 100Hz to 20kHz in the 30s. This trial aimed to showcase the performance of ADC chipsets at various frequencies.
- Spike train: biphasic pulse with a pulse width of 720 s at a rate of 7 pulses per second. This trial aimed to simulate the the performance of ADC chipset when acquiring neuromodulation artifacts.

2.4 Spectral Decomposition

The waveform obtained in the first trial was processed using a continuous wavelet transform (CWT). We used an analytic Morse wavelet with 10 voices per octave and an L1 normalization. For the signal recorded in the second trial we have computed the Welch power spectral density (PSD) estimate using a Hamming window.

3 DISCUSSION

A correct choice of an EEG acquisition system is crucial for a proper study design. Depending on the intended application, specific characteristics of the system should be accounted for. One of the most important components in this matter is the system's ADC. As we show empirically in this study, this component can prevent aliasing when facing out of band frequencies. Alternatively, we could predict this outcome by recurring to technical manuals provided by Texas Instruments. These contain theoretical bode magnitude plots for both filters (Figure 4). From these plots we can deduce that at Nyquist ADS1278 installed in the system 1 attenuates approximately 1011 stronger than the system 2. Furthermore, the attenuation offered by the ADS1298 is far weaker overall which is what leads to the results we obtained empirically. This increase in filter performance comes at the cost of an increase in the group delay. System 1 is equipped with a low pass filter that introduces a delay of 39 samples, while system 2 only has a sync3, delaying the recording by only 3 samples. That is, at a sampling rate of 1kSPS, system 1 will be lagging by 39ms while system 2 will lag by only 3ms. A correct timing is crucial in certain applications such as brain-computer interface (Kohrs et al., 2016) or localization of epileptogenic zones in people with epilepsy (Harris et al., 1994). This might also present an issue when studying inter-signal phase shift analysis of data acquired simultaneously from different devices, e.g. photoplethysmography (PPG) and electrocardiography.

4 LIMITATIONS

It is important to mention that the anti-aliasing filter is not enough to completely remove the artifact and other tools should be utilized in order to achieve a cleaner signal(Lio et al., 2018).

5 FUTURE WORKS

We will be performing this test on any other available EEG or high-density EEG system (menace). We will also be adapting the methodology for other systems such as MEG.

6 CONCLUSION

We proposed a simple test of suitability of an EEG acquisition system for neurostimulation studies. This test verifies whether the recorded EEG is majorly contaminated by an aliased stimulation artifact, but it does not guarantee an artifact-free recording. As we have shown in the results section, some artifact will still be included, especially when analyzing signals at frequencies higher than one third of the sampling frequency. We have tested two research-grade high-density EEG acquisition systems and selected a better performing one using time-frequency analysis.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Flowchart illustrating the experimental setup. A known signal is simulated using MATLAB and generated via the soundcard. The signal flows into the bucket containing the EEG cap and encounters the EEG cap. The Analog-to-Digital (ADC) Chip contains the anti-aliasing filter which is applied to the signal as it recorded by the EEG machine

Figure 2. CWT scalograms of A) synthetic chirp emitted by the soundboard, B) signal acquired by the system 1 equipped with ADS1278, C) signal acquired by the system 2, featuring the ADS1298. System 1 has minor aliasing at frequencies close to Nyquist but performs well when the soundboard emits frequencies above 600Hz. In turn, system 2 starts aliasing at frequencies as low as 128Hz, conserving this behavior until 1500Hz. Latter also presents sidelobes due to the sinc3 filter.

Figure 3. Welch estimate of the PSD of A) spike train generated by the soundboard, B) signal acquired by the system 1 equipped with ADS1278, C) signal acquired by the system 2, featuring the ADS1298. The spike train was generated as a biphasic wave with a pulse width of 720 uS at 7 pulses per second. The reflected harmonics, highlighted by the arrows in panels B and C, can be observed in both systems. The signal recorded by system 2 is contaminated at frequencies much below the Nyquist. Anti-aliasing filter of system 1 handles contamination at frequencies below 280Hz.

Figure 4. Theoretical Bode magnitude plots of anti-aliasing filters of both ADCs. ADS1278 reaches an attenuation of 120dB at Nyquist, whereas ADS1298 only reaches 10dB. Furthermore, ADS1298’s attenuation at frequencies above the frequency of sampling is significantly lower than that provided by ADS1298.